

Title: Design of a multi-use marine area off-shore the Mediterranean Sea

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Abstract:

The existing pressures on coastal areas are prompting the off-shore transfer of economic activities such as aquaculture, transportation, tourism, energy, leading to new challenges for the sustainable use of the sea and calling for integration of different activities in the same area. This paper conceptually designs a multi-use off-shore area in a mild sea, whose purpose is the setup of an energetically self-sustained fish farm. The climate conditions for aquaculture and renewable energy production are assessed first. The features and production of the fish farm are then designed, as well as the renewable energy system offering the power support. A new dedicated tool is presented and adopted for the setup and sizing of the electrical system required for the power stabilisation and energy supply in case the multi-use area is not grid-connected. The layout and payback time of the multi-use are finally examined, showing that wave energy systems are still far to make such installation economically competitive.

1 Introduction

The population growth and the related food request together with the rapid growth of the aquaculture sector and the already dramatic anthropogenic pressures in coastal areas are calling for the off-shore transfer of aquaculture activities. However, the siting of fish farms and aquaculture at relevant distance from shore requires a design based on remote-controlled machineries to avoid the

intensification of vessel traffic and related environmental impacts and to reduce the overall farming costs. This approach should rely in turns on local energy production, to avoid long cables and related risks, energy losses and again environmental impacts.

The off-shore integration of different activities such as aquaculture and renewable energy may lead to technological benefits, such as a common grid infrastructure, foundations or substructure, to shared logistics, operation and maintenance with the reduction of the costs, and to a common regulatory framework for more coordinated maritime spatial planning and a more streamlined licensing procedure.

The combination of aquaculture and wind farms has been analysed by several authors, amongst other: Buck et al. (2010); Barteling et al. (2014); Gimpel et al. (2015). The MERMAID (www.mermaidproject.eu), TROPOS (www.troposplatform.eu) and H2Ocean (www.h2ocean-project.eu) projects, funded by the European Commission under the call FP7-OCEAN2011-1, developed design concepts for a next generation of offshore platforms for multi-use of ocean space for energy extraction, aquaculture and platform related transport (Zanuttigh et al., 2015; Zanuttigh et al., 2016; Stuiver et al., 2016; van den Burg et al., 2016). The recent H2020 projects MARIBE and MUSES investigated the potential of a variety of different combinations of economic activities in co-location or integrated in platforms (van den Burg et al., 2019; Bocci et al., 2019; Dalton et al., 2020). The H2020 MARIBE project concluded that further funding for multi-use should be provided, to get through the next stage of development and bring multi-use through the so-called Valley of Death. In practice, multiple barriers are hampering implementation of multi-use, related to regulatory, financing, liability and insurance issues; environmental concerns; stakeholder perceptions; and lack of appropriate skills. Nowadays, there are very few examples of multi-purpose installations, typically in connection to offshore wind farms, the more advanced in Europe being the pilot realised in the North Belgian Sea, the EDULIS project (<http://www.aqua.ugent.be/edulis>), that is producing mussels in between a wind park at about 20 km from the coast.

This paper specifically aims at demonstrating the potential synergies in terms of resources exploitation and design layout, which can be achieved by integrating different uses in a multi-use area at a given off-shore site. It also aims at presenting the complex electrical system required to make the multi-use area standing alone, avoiding the huge costs due to the grid connection to the shore.

The selected site for the application is located off-shore Venice, Northern Adriatic Sea, Italy. The area is particularly challenging for multi-use as it is characterised by i) mild wind and wave climate; ii) high anthropogenic pressures due to maritime routes, existing off-shore infrastructures, high population and economic activities; iii) high social sensitivity due to inland cultural heritage preservation; iv) fragile ecosystems, including protected benthic communities and mammal routes.

The paper structure is as follows. After this Introduction (Section 1), Section 2 describes the site where the hypothetical off-shore installation would be placed, including the climate conditions, the environmental context and the legal constraints. The requirements, the configuration and the production of the fish farm are analysed in Section 3. Section 4 considers the exploitation of renewable energy from wind and waves. Section 5 addresses the local use of the produced energy to feed the fish farm and the electrical components required for the power stability; it also presents the analysis of the energy balance as implemented in the new tool. Section 6 presents the layout of the

multi-use area and a synthetic economic feasibility assessment. Finally, some conclusions about the multi-use synergies and the challenges to be still overcome are drawn in Section 7.

2 Description of the site

This Section provides an overview of the environment, of the climate and of the ecological conditions of the area selected for a hypothetical MU installation in Italy. The area hydro-morphological features, the principal marine communities and characteristic vertebrates are presented in Sub-section 2.1. The typical and extreme wind and wave climate are shown in Sub-section 2.2 and the climate conditions favourable to the fish farming are assessed in Sub-section 2.3. The legal constraints that regulate installations in terms of the exploitation of aquaculture and renewable energy are reported in Sub-section 2.4.

2.1 Overview of the site

The North Adriatic Sea is a shallow semi-enclosed basin. It has an average inclination of 0.35 m/km and an average depth of 40 m. It is characterised by sharp water column stratification and very high productivity rates (Artioli et al., 2005). The cyclonic circulation is very variable according to the season, and principally driven by the prevailing winds (NE and SE, see Sub-section 2.2) and by river discharge. The most significant influence being from the Po river with an annual average rate of 1700 m³/s. Fine sediments consist mainly of mud. The average coarse sediment fraction (>63µm) is generally lower than 8% of the dry weight.

The North Adriatic Sea is a strategic marine vertebrate conservation area and is home to large seabird populations (Zotier et al. 1999, Baccetti et al. 2002). Soft-bottom macrofaunal assemblages at deep sites (>20 m depth) have been characterized by Gamulin-Brida (1974) as belonging to muddy Detritic Bottoms (DE, Pérès et Picard, 1964). In front of Chioggia and up to to Grado, there are hard bottom areas called "*tegnue*" which are supporting concretions of benthic organisms, recently classified as coralligenous habitats (Casellato & Stefanon, 2008). As for marine mammals, today, the only regular component of the Northern Adriatic cetacean fauna is the common bottlenose dolphin (*Tursiops truncatus*) (Bearzi et al., 2004). The area is also an extremely important summer feeding area for loggerhead turtles (*Caretta caretta*).

The area selected for this hypothetical installation is off the Venice coast in the Northern Adriatic Sea (Italy). The site has a number of challenging issues, the most relevant being the following:

- it is one of the areas characterised by the lower marine energy in the Mediterranean, and therefore it is unlikely that a single purpose installation for energy conversion would be economically feasible;
- the infrastructure of the area is well developed, and the presence of harbours, commercial and touristic maritime routes suggests that there may be a potential conflict of use;
- the huge anthropogenic pressure (including existing offshore platforms) is causing environmental issues such as very high levels of eutrophication;
- the proximity to Venice increases the social attention regarding the implementation of new infrastructure.

In the Veneto Region fishery and aquaculture traditionally play a major role in terms of number of employees, dedicated vessels, and revenues. The markets of Tronchetto (Venice) and Chioggia are among the biggest in the North-Eastern Italy for fresh seafood, with respectively 8896 and 11390 tons of traded fresh seafood in 2016. The most recent data on the seafood sector trend, dating 2016 (AA.VV., 2016), indicate that the local production is deficitary, being the value of the total exported and imported seafood equal respectively to 115 Meuros and 918 Meuros. The aquacultural marine fish specifically showed a negative trend of -40%, that is mostly due to the decrease of the traditional lagoon aquacultural production, whose costs and yields are no longer competitive with recent sea cages practices in other Mediterranean areas. Only the long-line bivalves farming sector in offshore waters recorded a significant increase (+85%) in the period 2006-2016. Therefore the Venice area has a strong market potential, together with availability of qualified labour force for offshore fish farming, either coming from the traditional aquaculture sector and from fishery.

The location of the site and the bathymetry of the study area are shown in Fig. 2.1.1. As anticipated, the area is of special cultural, technical and industrial interest due to the presence of the city of Venice, threatened by the high waters, the harbour of Venice and the industrial port of Marghera. The most important environmental features of the area include:

- micro-tidal environment (< 1m tide);
- semi-enclosed basin (average incline 0.35 m/km, average depth 40 m);
- high seasonal hydrological variability, sharp stratification and very high productivity rates;
- high population density, tourism;
- eutrophication, pollution, extensive development of marine and coastal infrastructure, *a. O.* 100 offshore gas platforms in sedimentary environments (~10-120m) in the Northern Adriatic Sea.

Figure 2.1.1 – Location of the site (left panel) and bathymetry of the study area (right panel). The two points indicate the position of the Acqua Alta monitoring platform and the position of the hypothetical MU installation.

2.2 Wind and wave climate: typical and extreme conditions

The selected site for the MU is near to the Acqua Alta monitoring platform (45°18'51'' N; 12°30'30'' E), held by the Italian National Research Council (http://www.ismar.cnr.it/infrastructures/piattaforma-acqua-alta?set_language=en&cl=en). This platform is located 16 km off the coastline of Venice, on a water depth of 16 m (right panel of Fig. 2.1.1). The wind and wave data, collected at the site are from 1992 to 2008.

Figure 2.2.1 shows the mean annual wind (left panel) and wave (right panel) regimes by means of the frequency/direction/intensity diagram (i.e. rose diagram). Mean wind velocities V_w and significant wave heights H_s indicate two main directions: North East (Bora, between 0°N and 85°N) and South East (Scirocco, between 105°N and 175°N). The Bora direction is the most dominant in terms of intensity and frequency. The mean values of V_w range between 3 and 4 m/s at a height of 25 m, with a corresponding estimated $V_w = 4.54$ m/s at a height of 100 m (DNVGL-RP-C205). The only available resource appears to be relatively limited, as Orecca FP7 project (www.orecca.eu) defined a minimum value of 6 m/s at hub height for the feasibility of wind energy installations at a given site.

The maximum measured value of H_s is a little greater than 4 m and the calm period is close to 40% (if calm wave conditions are considered as those associated to $H_s < 0.25$ m). This is in keeping with the wave features found in the North Adriatic, i.e. a semi-enclosed basin with comparatively small fetches. The wave energy potential can be evaluated by computing the existing energy power per unit of wave front P_w using the following equation:

$$P_w = \frac{1}{64\pi} \rho g^2 H_s^2 T_e \quad (1)$$

The mean annual wave power available is approximately 1.1 kW/m, which is about one order of magnitude less than the typical available at the wave energy deployments in Northern Europe.

Figure 2.2.2 and 2.2.3 show the yearly (left panels) and monthly (right panels) variability respectively of P_w and V_w . The yearly values of P_w and V_w are higher and quite stable over the last 7 years of measurements with respect to the overall 16 years period. The results for the period 2001-2007 are here considered to be the reference values representing the recent trends of P_w and V_w . The yearly values are in the range 0.95-1.35 kW/m for P_w and 5-5.9 m/s for V_w . Lower seasonal variability can be observed for wind velocity, while P_w drops around 0.8 kW/m during the spring and summer period and increases above 1.2 kW/m in extreme winter conditions.

The Peak Over Threshold method was used to assess extreme conditions. Threshold values of $V_w=20.0$ m/s and $H_s=2.5$ m were assumed and three Probability Density Functions were adopted in order to obtain the design parameter as a function of the return period (Tr), i.e. the Gumbel, Frechet and GEV. The Frechet and GEV distribution gave a better fit with empirical observations of V_w and H_s respectively. The values of $V_w=29.4$ m/s and $H_s=3.9$ m are found for $Tr=100$ years.

Figure 2.2.1 – Mean annual wind (left) and wave (right) regime (rose diagram), based on measurements taken at the Acqua Alta platform from 1992-2007.

Figure 2.2.2 – Mean annual (left panel) and mean monthly (right panel) wave energy power per unit of wave front based on measurements at the Acqua Alta platform.

Figure 2.2.3 – Mean annual (left panel) and mean monthly (right panel) wind velocity V_w based on measurements at the Acqua Alta platform.

2.3 Climate conditions for aquaculture and fish farming

The threshold of 10 kts of wind is usually kept by aquaculture operators as the limit at which all operation involving the presence of workers on the floating cage collars can be safely done. This limit can be identified within the Beaufort scale at point 3, where an Hs of 0,6 m is expected under the Douglas scale of sea state of 3. At 15 kts of wind, only operation from board (e.g. feeding) can be safely run, within a Beaufort scale of 4 and a wave range of 1.5 to 2.5 m, corresponding to a Douglas sea state of 3-4. Beyond these thresholds, the use of a stand-alone feeding system (a feeding barge) is mandatory to be able to feed fish stocks even under moderately harsh sea states, thus taking advantage of the maximum number of favourable days with respect to water temperature, to reach production goals.

The analysis of the water temperature based on Copernicus data (<http://marine.copernicus.eu/services-portfolio/access-to-products/>) showed that favourable feeding days at the site are restricted within the April-December window, for a total of approx. 270 days/year, during the period 2016-2020. Outside of this window, the low temperature and the associated low feed intake by fish and the corresponding low growth rate makes feeding opportunity rather inconstant.

Based on the wind data at the Aqua Alta station, the number of days exceeding the 15 kts threshold is equal to 225 days within the interval April-December. Therefore, beyond other considerations about the site distance and the associated logistic costs, the use of a standing-alone system is mandatory to assure the exploitation of the remaining 45 days of favourable thermal conditions. The days below the 10 kts threshold are evenly distributed along all months, with an average of 19,1 days/month, allowing for maintenance activities and harvesting throughout the whole productive year, therefore positively qualifying the site for a large scale farming installation.

Figure 2.2.4 – Average number of days/months with wind velocities below 10 and 15 knots.

2.4 Legal framework of the hypothetical installation

Based on the Italian law, the peripheral regional agencies are in charge of all the functions related to the maritime State property (i.e. within 12 Maritime Miles). According to the legislation of the Veneto Region, the peripheral offices of *Genio Civile* are in charge of the concession demands for the maritime use. The environmental and social impacts assessment is coordinated by the Ministry of Environment, and for the incentives and subsidies of the off-shore installation are under competence of the Ministry of Industry. The current cost for leasing an off-shore aquacultural site is 0,004 Euro/m².

Regarding fish farming, the Legislative Decree No.154 of 2004, Art. 12 (7) on the *Modernization of the fisheries and aquaculture sectors* states that this area is of high ecological relevance for the conservation of biodiversity and of biological resources. Due to these environmental constraints, the hypothetical installation is moved off-shore the Acqua Alta Tower, on a 28 m depth (45°17'30"N, 12°42'15"E). However, the same wind and wave climate reconstructed at the Acqua Alta Tower are supposed to hold, especially due to the mild climate conditions.

3 Offshore fish farm design

This Section aims at presenting the conceptual design of the fish farm, including the species (Sub-section 3.1), the main design requirements (Sub-section 3.2) and the production and layout (Sub-section 3.3).

3.1 Selection of the species

In the last decades, marine aquaculture technology has considerably improved its capability to cope with harsh offshore conditions, aiming at gaining new spaces to an expanding industry, reducing conflicts with other uses of the sea, and at the same time improving farming conditions and waste dilution in open waters. To select the most promising species for fish farming in the area, the data of the sea water temperature at the free surface and at -8 m depth were derived from Copernicus web site (<http://marine.copernicus.eu/services-portfolio/access-to-products/>) in the period from 2008 to 2018. The lowest values recorded, below 13 ° for a considerable time span, has led to the exclusion of the Gilthead Seabream as candidate for fish production at the site, being largely below its physiological optimal range in winter. A second candidate species, the Sea Bass, can normally handle these temperatures, and it is commonly farmed in the Northern Adriatic Sea, and widely widespread in lagoons and in coastal areas throughout all the year. The farming know-how of the Sea Bass in the Mediterranean aquaculture industry has been available over the past +30 years, and this species has a steadily increasing demand in the global markets as fresh product.

3.2 Design requirements

The following basic requirements should be taken into account when installing and operating a Sea Bass fish farm:

- in order to secure a good waste dilution to the fish stock, the water depth at the site should be ideally be around 30 m or deeper, in presence of a significant water current. The minimum required depth by the Italian legislation is 20 m.
- individual cages must be as far as possible from the nearest cages, to allow good circulation of clean water between and within cages.
- Sedimentary bottoms are preferred, due to the reduced impact on benthic biocenosis and to the greater ease of mooring installation and tensioning.

For the specific case study, these additional requirements are set to accomplish the site features and allow for a profitable exploitation:

- cages and related installations must cope with $H_s=4.0$ m, corresponding to a 50 years return period, following NS9145 standard;
- intense automation for offshore services, mainly feed distribution;
- annual gross profitability in a range of 20-30% of total revenues;
- farming area within 1,5 Mm²;
- port distance within 15 nm;
- depth of 25 m.

It is assumed that large seafood markets in the area and in the surrounding Northern Italian regions are able to absorb the estimated production.

3.3 The fish-farm production and layout

The fish farm layout (Fig. 3.3.1) consists of 30 cages of 30 m diameter, which are grouped in 3 frames of 10 cages each. Each cage is placed in a mooring system, whose squared frame has a side of 60 m, moored to the bottom with mooring lines 100 m long. The fish farming area is about 1.2 km², accounting for the space between neighbouring wave parks, that should be at least of 100 m for free sailing of the fish farm service and other maintenance vessels. Cages of the selected size are rated even for higher H_s that in the present site, and are perfectly able to withstand very harsh meteocean condition without the needs of any shelter. Farms operating floating cages are successfully in place since several years in Italy, Tunisia, Algeria, Spain, Malta. The selected mooring frame has the peculiar feature of being able to act as an integrated elastic system, distributing loads on several mooring line depending from the incidence angle, and, in case of line failure, diverting loads on adjacent lines avoiding excessive cage deformations. Tensioning is a critical operation to ensure proper mooring response, and an eventual use of a fixed mooring point (e.g. a platform leg) may impair the possibility of line re-tensioning by simply anchor displacement, thus adding an unnecessary complexity to mooring management (Turnet, 2000).

The average production size selected for the Sea Bass is 400 g, which is estimated to require 18 months of growth. Considering a Coefficient of Variation CV of 25% for the entire production, this allows to yield for each cage the quantities and sizes as in Tab. 3.3.1. Based on a production estimate of 150 ton/cycle for each cage, and including a harvesting period of some months, the gross revenue for each cage is 1'178'500 €/2years. Therefore, the gross revenue for 30 cages is 17'677'500 €/year, corresponding to 2'250 ton/year of fish production.

The feeding platform is placed in the centre of the farm, at the maximum distance of about 600 m from the cages, which is easily manageable by the modern feeding machineries. The power required for the feed delivery is estimated between in 50 kW for each blowing system; following a principle of machinery redundancy for critical applications, a dedicated blower + feeding system is envisaged for each group of 10 cages. Given the maximum feeding consumption of 40 ton/day, the machinery working time will be not less than 8 hours/day, from April to December included. The fish farm is aligned to the direction of the most intense waves from Bora and Scirocco, sheltering the feeding platform from wave trains coming from North East.

Fig. 3.3.1 Fish farm layout.

Tab. 3.3.1 Fish production per cage and size, considering the prices between 6 and 11 €/kg.

Commercial category	% of category, at 400 g average and CV 25%	Price (€) per category	Yield (ton) per cage	Gross revenue (€)
Sea Bass 200-300 g	16.5%	6,00	24.7	148'200
Sea Bass 300-400 g	33%	7,00	49.5	346'500
Sea Bass 400-500 g	33%	9,00	49.5	455'500
Sea Bass 500-600 g	14.5%	9,00	21.7	195'300
Sea Bass 600-700 g	2%	11,00	3.0	33'000
Total revenue/cage				1'169,3
Total revenue/farm				17'538,8

4 Assessment of the available marine energy resources

This Section aims at assessing the available energy from wave (Sub-section 4.1) and wind (Sub-section 4.2) and the potential energy production, given the selected devices: WaveStar and Libellula turbine. The produced energy is meant to be used to support the fish farm in order to make a standing-alone multi-use marine area.

4.1 Wave Energy harvesting

4.1.1 Characteristics of the selected device

There are currently more than 100 types of Wave Energy Converters (WECs) at different stages of development from concept to demonstration. Each WEC is characterized by a particular method of operation that leads to different amount of electricity for a specific set of wave conditions. Previous extensive literature review studies (Koca et al., 2013) suggest only few WECs (10) to be retained for off-shore and near-shore installation: Pelamis, Oyster, Dexa, Wave Dragon, OE Buoy, Wave Bob, Seabased, Aws II, PowerBuoy, Wavestar.

Since the purpose here is the design of an off-shore installation, on-shore and/or bottom-based devices (such as Oyster, Seabased, PowerBuoy) have to be discarded. Furthermore, devices based on the overtopping concept, such as the Wave Dragon, or wave activated bodies, such as Pelamis and Dexa, are not appropriate due to the mild climate (low wave height, limited wave steepness). Floating point absorbers (such as OE Buoy, Wave Bob, Aws II) are also discarded because of the high cost of moorings

The WaveStar (<http://wavestarenergy.com>) is therefore selected due to the following features that makes it particularly suited for the site, specifically:

- it is a point absorber, therefore it can extract energy from all the incoming wave directions;
- it produces energy also for mild wave heights (> 0.5m);
- it is suggested for installations on a water depth up to 25 m;
- its structure allows construction synergies when combined with other functionalities (e.g. wind turbines).

The Wave Star harvests energy from its floaters moving up and down following the waves crests and troughs (<http://wavestarenergy.com/concept>). The motion of the floaters is converted into the motion of an hydraulic piston and then into the rotation of a generator, producing electricity. The floaters are attached to arms that integrate all the electrical and mechanical components and the arms are in turns attached to a platform. The platform is fixed on piles drilled into the seabed. The platform height with respect to the mean sea level should be such to avoid overflow during extreme storms (see Fig. 4.1.1). The platform length should be at least equal to the typical wavelength at the site, so that the wave amplitude can be fully exploited by the series of floaters.

The full-scale commercial WEC, Wave Star C5-600 kW, is supposed to consist of 20 floaters (10 on each side of the platform) and to be installed within the range of water depths of 15-30 m (Kramer et al., 2011).

Figure 4.1.1 – View of the 1:5 WaveStar prototype in operation and in survival mode

4.1.2 Estimate of the energy production and configuration

The power production is derived from the available literature on the numerical and physical modelling of the WaveStar performance and from the prototype measurements (Rambøll, 2004; Kramer et al., 2011).

The floater power $P_{floater}$ is estimated from the measured correlation of the power produced at the prototype by two hydraulic actuators with the wave height H_s :

$$P_{floater} = \frac{1}{2} H_s^{2.08} \quad (3)$$

Eq. (3) should be indeed corrected to account for the effect of the average wave period T_m , that was investigated by measuring $P_{floater}$ with increasing T_m and keeping H_s constant (Rambøll, 2004). The effect of T_m is significant only for $T_m > 4s$ and produces an increase of $P_{floater}$. Therefore Eq. (3) leads to cautious estimates of $P_{floater}$, especially considering that the local wave climate is characterized by relatively short waves.

Based on the numerical investigations by Rambøll (2004), the power losses (P_{loss1}) due to the presence of multiple floaters can be represented by the following function of the wave direction:

$$P_{loss1} = 0.004 \cdot \alpha_a + 0.711 \quad (4)$$

where the angle α_a is the angle between the arm of the floaters and the incoming wave direction. The power losses P_{loss2} induced by the wave obliquity (Rambøll, 2004) are given by:

$$P_{loss2} = 0.003 \cdot \alpha_a + 0.710 \quad (5)$$

The lower the α_a (around 0° , i.e. waves acting parallel to the arms) the lower the power reduction and the higher the value of P_{loss2} .

The starting point for the design here is a platform with $n_{floater}=10$ along each side and $D=6$ m, smaller than the commercial machine but keeping the same size of the floaters (Frigaard et al., 2016). As a compromise between the power losses due to floater interference (Rambøll, 2004) and the marine occupied space, the gap width $G_{floater}$ in between adjacent floaters is assumed to be $G_{floater}=D/2$.

The basic platform length $L_{plat}=60$ m results from

$$L_{Plat} = \frac{n_{floater}}{2} \cdot D + \left(\frac{n_{floater}}{2} - 2\right) \cdot G_{floater} + 20$$

where the last term accounts for a rough estimate of the space required to the side of the floaters for the foundations and/or to combine each single platform with other platforms characterized by a different orientation.

Based on the analysis of the wave climate, at least 2 platforms are required, to derive energy from the prevailing Bora and Scirocco directions. In order to maximise the power production at the site, a third platform is also introduced. The NE and SE platforms are placed with the axis as perpendicular as possible to the two main wave directions, i.e. at 30° N and 150° N for the NE and the SE platform respectively. The third platform is assumed to be placed at equal distance with respect to the other two ones, in order to minimise the layout-floaters interference, see the configuration schematised in Fig. 4.1.2. The geometrical characteristics of the module are synthesised in Table 4.1.1.

The power production of a single module P_{module} is derived –for each wave measurement– as the sum of the power production of the three platforms P_{Plat} .

The contribution of each platform P_{Plat} is computed by combining Eq. (3), Eq. (4) and Eq. (5):

$$P_{Plat1} = P_{floater} \cdot n_{floater} \cdot P_{loss1,1} \cdot P_{loss2,1} \quad (10)$$

The annual energy production E of the single module is then derived as the product of P_{Module} by the operational time T_o .

The average value of the annual electricity production E_{wave} of the WaveStar module equals 123 MWh/y, with an average $T_o=30\%$ and an average module efficiency $\eta=39\%$ (see Figure 4.1.3). The average contribution of the 3 platforms to the module production is very similar, being the 33%, the 36% and the 31% from platform 1 to 3. The available average P_w is 1,04 kW with a standard deviation of 0,20. Seasonality effects are particularly evident, with very limited energy production from April to August and maximum production during Autumn, see Figure 4.1.4.

The more recent research available on the WaveStar production (Frigaard et al., 2016) provides the power matrix for a commercial 600 kW machine, consisting of a single platform with 20 floaters of 6 m diameter. The combination of this matrix, with the available tool for the assessment of the energy production (Chozas et al., 2014) and with the typical wave climate at the site (Zanuttigh et al., 2016), leads to $E=82$ MWh/y, given a reduced number of 10 floaters and a power take off efficiency equal to 70%. This estimate however disregards the losses for floaters interference and for wave obliquity. A general reduction coefficient of 0,6 is proposed in case of a complex layout consisting of 3 platforms, independently from their orientation with respect to the waves. By keeping constant the size of the wave power capture mechanism, 3 platforms with 10 floaters would then lead to $E=148$ MWh/y, a figure that is about 1,15 times the average value of E derived over the 20 years with the previous analysis that proves to be more cautious than the more recent findings.

Figure 4.1.2 – Scheme of the Wave Star Module with an angle of 120° between the platforms, and the platform in the direction of the more energetic waves oriented at 30°N.

Table 4.1.1 – Geometrical configuration for the floaters, the platform and the module

Description	Nomenclature	Value
Floater diameter	D	6 m
Number of floaters for a single platform (both sides)	n_{floater}	10
Distance between two adjacent floater	G_{floater}	3 m
Platform length	L_{plat}	60 m
Platform width	-	12 m
Number of platforms	-	3
Configuration	Module	-
Platform1 orientation	-	30° N
Platform2 orientation	-	150° N
Platform3 orientation	-	270° N

Figure 4.1.3 Operational time T_o , efficiency η and annual electricity production E of the WaveStar module designed for the installation off-shore Venice over the 20 years of data.

Figure 4.1.4 Operational time T_o , efficiency η and monthly electricity production of the WaveStar module designed for the installation off-shore Venice over 2007.

4.2 Wind Energy exploitation

4.2.1 Characteristics of the selected wind turbine

To maximise the energy production and the synergies of the construction without compromising the structural stability, and to minimise the footprint impact, one 55 kW Libellula turbine is supposed to be installed at the centre of each module of the WaveStar.

The available data of wind velocities at the CNR platform v_{CNR} are measured at the reference height $z_0=25$ m above swl. The wind velocities for each turbine v_{HUB} are therefore transferred to the hub height/s z_{Hub} by means of the hypothesis of fully turbulent flow

$$v_{Hub} = v_{CNR} \cdot \frac{\ln\left(\frac{z_{Hub}}{m}\right)}{\ln\left(\frac{z_0}{m}\right)}, \quad (2)$$

where $m=2 \times 10^{-4}$ m is the surface roughness parameter in open sea and $z_{Hub}=29$ m for the Libellula 55 kW turbine. In order to obtain the power P for each turbine, the minimum velocity for the power production start $v_{min}=3$ m/s, the maximum velocity for the turbine standby $v_{off}=20$ m/s, the threshold velocity $v_{thr}=10$ m/s, that defines the start of the maximum asymptotic power production, and the typical power production curve are derived from the constructor.

The Libellula power production curve is expressed as

$$\begin{cases} P = 0 & \text{for } v_{Hub} < v_{in} \\ P = 0.9363 \cdot v_{Hub}^2 - 5.3304 \cdot v_{Hub} + 7.8351 & \text{for } v_{in} < v_{Hub} < v_{thr} \\ P = 55 & \text{for } v_{thr} < v_{Hub} < v_{off} \\ P = 0 & \text{for } v_{Hub} > v_{off} \end{cases}$$

4.2.2 Energy production and operational windows

The estimated yearly energy production and operation time are synthesised in Figure 4.2.1. There is quite a high yearly variation of power production across the years, being the average value of the annual wind energy production equal to 82 MWh/y. At least in the recent years the operational time T_0 is more stable than the power production, being always greater than 70% since 1999. This figure is indeed quite high and shows how far wind energy can complement wave energy at the site, whose T_0 is about the half. The monthly variation of power production is also high, as shown in Figure 4.2.2. The power production drops to less than the 50% for about 3 months/year. The wind energy production would be therefore very limited and can be considered only in combination with other devices and/or infrastructures, as in this case.

Figure 4.2.1 Yearly power production and operational time windows for Libellula wind turbine in the period 1993-2007.

Figure 4.2.2 Percentage monthly power production (non-dimensionalised with the maximum occurred in January) for Libellula wind turbine in 2005.

5 Energy production and local storage

This Section explores the possibility of a standing-alone installation since the connection to the shore represents one of the higher costs of the multi-use area, especially in presence of a limited energy resource, so that it might be impossible to recover the capital costs in a reasonable time. This Section presents also a new tool capable of a long term energy balance analysis, based on a time series of met-ocean data (measured or from a hind-cast model) and on power consumption estimation. Specifically, Sub-section 5.1 gives an overview of the electrical power system required for the standing-alone solution, Sub-section 5.2 describes more in details the functioning and the components of the electrical system and Sub-section 5.3 presents the energy balance analysis solved by the new tool and illustrates the results of the new tool applied to this multi-use area.

5.1 The electrical power system for the standing-alone solution

In case the multi-use area is connected to the grid, given the estimated power capacity (<100 MW) and the distance from shore (<100 km), this multi-use will fall into the MVAC category. An offshore substation will collect array cables from different devices and to export power, including switchgears, control apparatus, compensation of reactive power, etc. A HV substation on the mainland will be required to obtain enough capacity for energy transport. Based on the minimum water depth (>20 m) needed for aquaculture, the distance to the closest HV substation will be in the order of 30-35 km (Chioggia).

In case the multi-use area is standing-alone, the power consumption of all the local loads deriving from aquaculture operations, lighting and any other offshore use must be lower than or equal to the energy extraction.

Advantages of the standing-alone configuration are:

- lack of substation and export cables, with consequent reduction of the environmental impact on the bottom and of the overall cost, which may also benefit from margins of reduction from array cables, depending on the extension of the multi-use ;
- boost of blue-growth, by using renewable energy instead of fossil fuel and therefore fostering a greener process; in this case of course the renewable production actually results into avoided expenses rather than into active incomes (no energy is sold to the grid), assuming that the renewable energy substitutes conventional diesel engines. A reference cost for the energy produced by diesel engines on Italian islands not interconnected with mainland ranges between 180 and 300 €/MWh.

On the other hand, an appropriate energy storage system is needed to manage the power balance of the multi-use area installation, since the Renewable Energy (RE) generation systems produce a variable and not fully predictable amount of electric energy.

In order to keep the electrical system stable, a power quality management system is required to provide all the services necessary to sustain voltage and frequency, such as primary, secondary and tertiary reserve and voltage regulation. The identification of the most suitable storage technology has to take into account the capability of the storage system itself to provide all of these services for the needed amount of time.

A detailed assessment is therefore needed in terms of:

- aquaculture power consumption at the site and typical uses across the day, considering the fish feeding system, the platform crane, the ice producing machines to sacrifice and chill harvested fishes before deliver them to the shore, the electric boats and floating vehicles, the lighting and ancillary services as communication, data acquisition, heat pumps, etc;
- time-series-based renewable energy power production, whose analysis will provide information on the most suitable technology in terms of Power and Energy capacity and suitability to cover a specific amount of power cycles.

The fish farm requires:

- a base load due to controls, monitoring and communication systems, having an average amount of 2 kW during each 3 hours intervals (note that 3 hours is the measurement time interval of the wave data so this is the maximum resolution of the time-series analysis),
- a variable electric load for the feeding system (150 Kw) during 8 hours in Winter and during 12 hours from Spring to Fall,
- an additional electric load (i.e. the ancillary loads in Fig. 5.1) of 50 Fw distributed over the 12 hour is expected, due to ice-making machines, a cold storage at 0-4°C, a desalination unit and a breathable air compressor for divers.

Therefore the following additional components have to be installed:

- a primary energy storage system in form of a Battery Pack (BP) capable to support voltage and frequency stability and supply the base load due to the ancillary systems;
- a Liquid Petroleum Gas fuelled Generator Set (GS) with rated power sufficient to supply all the platform related loads in every condition;
- a Dummy Load (DM), in form of an electric resistance pack controlled by a rectifier, that dissipates in air or water the power exceeding the multi-use platform balance and stabilizes the system frequency.

Moreover, an additional secondary storage system is designed to allow for a medium term storage of the RE produced in excess to the load request. This system, the hydrogen storage system (H₂), consists of a group of modular electrolysers producing low pressure hydrogen (35 bar) connected to the power bus, when the capacity of the BP is fully utilized. The produced hydrogen is stored in a pressurized tank, supplying priority hydrogen fuel to the GS.

The single wire layout of the multi-use global electric power system is here represented in Figure 5.1.

Fig. 5.1. Scheme of the multi-use electric power system – Electrical Single Wire diagram, including the hydrogen storage H₂, the Generator Set GenSet, the Battery Pack BP, the wind WTG and wave WEC energy converters, the Dummy Load and the Ancillary Loads.

5.2 The Energy Balance Model for the multi-use area

The stand-alone electrical system (Fig. 5.1) can be properly sized only based on the analysis of the real balance of the average power and energy over a time period. The need of such analysis is due mainly to:

- the variable RE generation with respect to the power request,
- the presence of the storage systems, BP and H₂, that adds “energy memory” to the system.

To this purpose, a new MS-Excel based tool has been developed, that can elaborate time-series long up to the spreadsheet capability in terms of rows number. Every step of the analysis takes into account the previous situation in terms of the stored energy. Given the available met-ocean data, the time-series here is 10 years long, with a 3-hour time interval. The analysis tool assumes that the power is constant and equal to the average over each time interval.

5.2.1 System’s Frequency and Voltage stability

The instantaneous electrical stability of the stand-alone system is not analysed here due to its negligible influence over the long-term energy balance.

To keep stable the electrical vector (frequency, Voltage) on the Low Voltage (LV) buses, in every time the following balances have to be verified:

$$\Sigma P_i = 0, \Sigma Q_i = 0$$

where P_i [kW] are the instantaneous Active Power generated or absorbed by the generators/loads and Q_i [KVAR] are the Reactive Power due to the inductive or capacitive behaviour of the same grid components.

The instantaneous balance of the active power P keeps the system frequency stable, assuming the RE generators as independent variables. When the GS is off, the system active power balance can be controlled by the action of the loads and of the storage systems, ever under the instantaneous overall control of the DM, able to remove every power surplus. Moreover, when the GS is on, it performs the frequency control of the insulated grid, without the need of the DM action.

The balance of the reactive power Q has influence on the voltage regulation of the network. The inverters and/or the other power electronic devices connected to the grid can act as Static Synchronous Compensators (STATCOMs) and supply or drain reactive power by the buses in order to keep the system's voltage into the consented window. When active, the GS can act as rotating synchronous compensator for Q as well.

5.2.2 The Battery Pack

The BP temporarily accumulates the produced energy that exceeds the energy required by the fish farm. The instantaneous maximum accumulation equals the difference between the maximum BP capacity and the current BP level, being zero of course when the BP is full.

The BP has to guarantee the base load (only basic ancillary loads, full time on) required by the fish farm in absence of RE production and may supply energy to the fish farm when the RE production is insufficient, avoiding the start of the GS in such particular condition. It is considered the installation of a 10 kW BP pack, characterised by a nominal capacity of 30 kWh.

The analysis tool computes step by step the State of Charge (SOC) of the BP and compares the SOC of the BP with these upper and lower limits:

$$SOC_{max} = k_1 \cdot BP_{capacity} \quad [\text{kWh}] \quad (\text{e.g. } k_1 = 0.9 \text{ p.u.})$$

$$SOC_{min} = k_2 \cdot BP_{capacity} \quad [\text{kWh}] \quad (\text{e.g. } k_2 = 0.2 \text{ p.u.})$$

If the SOC of the BP falls within the above defined SOC interval and the RE generated average power exceeds the loads request, then the BP can be charged. Otherwise, the BP supplies the basic ancillary loads to the multi-use area.

5.2.3 The Hydrogen storage system

The stand-alone MUP analysis tool considers a medium term hydrogen storage system composed by:

- a series of low-pressure electrolyzers, included the power electronic pack, having:
 - P_{H2} [kW] rated capacity (e.g. 25 kW);
 - h_{H2} [p.u] conversion efficiency defined as E_{H2}/E_{abs} (e.g. 0.8 p.u.), where E_{abs} is the specific energy due to the hydrogen produced by the electrolyzers and E_{H2} is the electric energy necessary for its production.
- a storage tank characterized by:
 - $SH2_{cap}$ [kWh] rated storage capacity @ rated pressure (e.g. 30 bar),

- SH_{2vol} [m^3] storage tank's volume,
- h_{SH2} [p.u] hydrogen storage cycle efficiency defined as E_{in}/E_{out} (e.g. 0.98 p.u.),
- zero initial capacity at time step 0.

5.2.4 The Generating Set

An autonomous Generating System GS guarantees the power to the fish farm in all possible conditions of RE generation. To avoid sea water pollution, the GS is supplied by Liquid Petroleum Gas (LPG). The gas fuelled GS can be supplied by hydrogen as well, or by a mixture of both H₂ and LPG.

As first approximation, the energy analysis tool assumes that the hydrogen produced by RE and stored into the pressure tank is used as the priority fuel supplying the GS engine, without mixture. The GS overall conversion efficiency is considered to be of the 37%.

The GS capacity (kVA) is dependent on the amount of all the load active and reactive power that should be necessarily supplied in any condition of RE availability, in details:

- the fish farm loads, mainly the feeders including the ancillary (lighting, control system, etc.)
- the ancillary system of the RE generating systems (WEC, WTG in Fig. 5.1)
- the ancillary systems of the services of the multi-use are such as control, communication, lighting, etc.

5.2.5 The Dummy Load

If the RE active power exceeds the instantaneous absorption of the loads, including BP (if not full), a series of modular electrolyser cells converting electricity in low pressured hydrogen (H₂) is activated. The residual exceeding power is then dissipated by the DM. The same DM could be functional to keep the instantaneous frequency/power stability of the insulated electrical system, giving some transient contributions in terms of power drainage as well, which is not considered here due to its duration less than the time-series interval.

5.3 The Energy Tool application and results

Figure 5.2 reports the balance of energy that is produced (wind and wave), dissipated (battery losses), used (fish farm, activation of the GS) and stored (hydrogen production) for each year of met-ocean measurements. Furthermore, the same figure shows the energy balance over the last 10 years by disregarding the almost constant base load due to the fish farming. The variability of energy production and the limited BP capacity can be appreciated, highlighting the necessity of the GS. When looking at the values reported in Figure 5.2, it has to be mentioned that a single module of the WaveStar, including one Libellula wind turbine, was considered in the calculation.

The generated energy, E_{GEN} , is calculated as the sum of the harvested renewable energy E_{wind} and E_{wave} already computed in the previous Section 4. The energy balance E_{Bal} is therefore expressed as

$$E_{Bal} = E_{GEN} - E_{Load} = E_{wind} + E_{wave} - E_{Load}.$$

E_{Load} is the load of the fish farm (see Section 3) and consists of two components

$$E_{Load} = 3 \cdot P_{Load} = 3 \cdot (P_{F1} + P_{F2})$$

where P_{F1} is the constant base load equal to 2 kW and P_{F2} is the variable load that equals $P_{Feed}=200\text{kW}$ for 8 hours/day from May to December and is zero otherwise.

The energy exchanged to/from the battery E_B is expressed as

$$E_B = |E_{Bal}| \cdot \eta_c \text{ if } E_{Bal} > 0 \text{ and}$$

$$E_B = |E_{Bal}| / \eta_d \text{ if } E_{Bal} < 0.$$

where $\eta_c=0,92$ and $\eta_d=0,95$ are the battery charge and discharge indicative efficiency respectively. The battery nominal capacity E_{Bn} is assumed equal to 30 kWh. The maximum energy stored $E_{Bmax}=k_b \cdot E_{Bn}$ is assumed no more than 27 kWh, assuming a safety factor $k_{bmax} = 0,9$ and the minimum $k_{bmin} = 0,2$ equal to 6 kWh. The battery rated power is $P_b = 10$ kW.

The State Of Charge indicator SOC in kWh indicates the energy stored into the battery pack at the different steps of the time series:

$$SOC = E_B(0) + S(E_B)$$

where $E_B(0)$ is the battery capacity at time $t=0$.

The energy dissipated during the charge cycle because of the battery losses E_{BL} is

$$E_{BL} = (SOC - E_B(0)) / \eta_{BP}$$

being the BP cycle efficiency $\eta_{BP} = \eta_c \cdot \eta_d = 0,92 \cdot 0,95 = 0,87$.

The GS is automatically switched on if the following power balance condition is verified:

$$|P_{GEN}| + |P_B| - |P_{Load}| < 0$$

where P_{GEN} , P_B and P_{Load} are the powers corresponding to the energies E_{GEN} , E_B and E_{Load} respectively.

The energy produced by the GS, E_{GS} , is given by

$$E_{GS} = |E_{Bal} - E_{BL}| \text{ if } E_{Bal} - E_{BL} < 0$$

$E_{GS}=0$ otherwise.

The hydrogen production is activated when:

$$P_{GEN} + P_B > P_{Load}.$$

For the hydrogen cycle, the following figures are assumed:

- production efficiency $\eta_p=0,80$;
- storage efficiency $\eta_s=0,98$;
- generation efficiency $\eta_g=0,37$;
- H2 electrolyser nominal power 25kW and maximum power P_{H2max} 300kW;
- n. 12 electrolyser of the same type;
- H2 storage capacity $SC_{H2}=5000$ kWh.

The State Of Charge SOC for the H2 cycle, $SOCH_2$, is the energy stored in form of pressured H2 into the tank. When the GS is activated, the model assumes that the H2 fuel is priority used, instead of the LPG. The value of $SOCH_2$ is derived from:

$$SOCH_2 = EH_{2P} - EH_{2GS} + EH_2(0)$$

where:

- $EH_2(0)=0$ is the content of the storage pressure gas tank at time $t=0$,
- EH_{2GS} is the energy produced by the GS that consumes by priority the hydrogen derived from renewables $EH_{2GS} = (E_{GEN} - E_{Load} - E_{BL}) / (\eta_G \cdot \eta_s)$,
- EH_{2P} is the energy transformed into hydrogen considering the efficiency of the electrolyzers, $EH_{2P} = 3 \cdot PH_{2P}$, where $PH_{2P} = P_{OV} \cdot \eta_P$ if $|P_{OV}| < P_{H2max}$ and $PH_{2P} = -P_{H2max}$ otherwise. The overflow power P_{OV} is derived from $P_{OV} = (E_{GEN} - E_{Load} - E_{BL} + E_{GS}) / 3 (\eta_G \cdot \eta_s)$.

The energy produced by the GS by using LPG, E_{GS_GAS} , is calculated as

$$E_{GS_GAS} = (EH_{2GS} - SOC_{H2}) \cdot (\eta_G \cdot \eta_s) \text{ if } SOC_{H2} > 1 \text{ and } SOC_{H2} < 1,$$

$$E_{GS_GAS} = E_{GS} \text{ if } SOC_{H2} < 1 \text{ and } P_{GS} > 1, \text{ being } P_{GS} = E_{GS} / 3.$$

The energy stored as excess of hydrogen production E_{GSH2} is calculated as

$$E_{GSH2} = E_{GS} - E_{GS_GAS} \text{ if } P_{GS} < 1, 0 \text{ otherwise.}$$

The energy dissipated E_{diss} is given by the excess of the energy production with respect to the loads of the fish farm, the BP capacity and the GS capacity:

$$E_{diss} = 3 \cdot (P_{OV} - PH_{2P}) \text{ if } SOC_{H2} < SC_{H2},$$

$$E_{diss} = 3 \cdot P_{OV} \text{ otherwise.}$$

The above balances are carried out for each step of the time series. The global energy values represented in Fig. 5.2 are the sum of the energies calculated over all the steps.

Fig. 5.2. Energy balance, specifically: E wave is the energy produced by one WaveStar module; E wind is the energy produced by a single Libellula wind turbine; E battery losses is the energy dissipated in the battery cycle; E GS_GAS is the energy produced by GS using natural gas fuel; E GS_H2 is the energy produced by GS using the hydrogen local production; Edissipated is the energy wasted by the Dummy Load when the energy production exceeds the fish farm requirements, the hydrogen production and the battery capacity.

A single Wave Star module including a single Libellula turbine is here considered. All the energies are in MWh/y.

6 Features of the Multi-Use area

This Section addresses some key features of the multi-use area, specifically the layout (Sub-section 6.1) and the costs (Sub-sections 6.2 and 6.3).

6.1 The synergic layout

The design of the multi-use area should optimise the use of the marine space while combining constraints related to each single use (such as minimum safety distances, maximum distances from the shore, required space for ordinary and extraordinary operation/maintenance, etc.) and desirable features (i.e. minimise the occupied space, protect aquaculture, maximise energy harvesting for wind and wave energy devices, etc.). The multi-use design has to account also for potential synergic use of components (piles, emerged supports, mooring lines, etc.) or indirect benefits deriving from different uses (e.g. wave absorption by WECs for protecting aquaculture installation), see Zanuttigh et al. (2016).

Certainly, the marine renewable devices offer some weak sheltering from waves. However, during severe storms, the Wavestar enters into survival mode and the floater are no longer interacting with the waves, so that the sheltering effect is limited to that of the jackets. During ordinary operational activities however, advantage can be taken from the sheltering effect. Accurate estimation of the transmission coefficient requires the use of accurate numerical models (Verao et al., 2019b) and/or laboratory models (Stratigaki et al., 2014).

The power required by the fish farm is about 200 kW for 6 hours during winter time and 12 hours during summer time, for a total of about 0.8 GWh/year, which is close to the production assured by 4 integrated units of WaveStar modules and Libellula wind turbines.

In order to protect the fish farm and to make the installation economically more attractive, given the distance from the shore (around 22 km at a 28 m water depth), the marine renewable energy farm is strictly limited to the required units, optimizing also the available footprint. The WaveStar integrated modules are aligned to protect from the direction of the most severe storms (Bora) over the greater bottom depth. The gap width among adjacent modules (taken between each centre) equals four times the platform length to minimize wake effects as advised by previous studies (Verao Fernandez et al., 2019a; Angelelli et. al., 2012).

The multi-use layout is shown in Figure 6.1.1. The total occupied marine space is about 1.3 km².

Figure 6.1.1 – Layout of the multi-use area. The WECs, including the wind turbines, are placed along Bora direction, to favour a sheltering effect for the fish farm.

6.2 Costs and revenues of the fish farm

The financial annual balance estimation is based on common methods used in agricultural balances, where revenues, costs and related indexes are derived from the expected growth and mortalities. Rates for depreciations, interests and insurances used are the commonest in agricultural administration practice (Iacopone and Romiti, 1986). Final tax rate cannot be simply calculated, being based on a number of figures, as VAT and taxes on enterprises' income and property values, and well beyond the scope of the present paper. An average rate (33%) over the final profit has been figured, to verify the persistence of a positive sign in final profits.

The proposed layout is based on an investment scheme where Capital Costs (CC) are estimated in 3,325 M(€), and Operating Costs (OC) are of 10,145 M(€), see table 6.2.1. Table 6.2.2 reports the annual estimated balance. The annual amount of 107.961€ of fuel related costs can therefore be the basis for further calculations on the opportunity and feasibility to divert to alternative energy source systems, also from the point of view of a long-term utilization, over the whole 10-years depreciation period.

Tab. 6.2.1 Capital and operating costs, in K(€)

	Capital costs	Operating costs
Machineries	5005,0	1427,2
Properties	320,0	31,5
Raw materials		7986,2
Site lease		5,2
Salaries		1174,2
Totals	5325,0	10167,4

Table 6.2.2 – Annual estimated balance, (€).

	Revenues (+)	Costs (-)	Profits (+/-)
Marketable fish value	17.538.750		
Machinery		1.337.232	
Property quotas		31.530	
Raw materials costs		7.986.206	
Staff costs		1.174.200	
Site lease cost		5.242	
Raw profit			+7.004.341
Taxation rate%	33		
Net profit			+ 4.692.908
% over Revenues			27 %

6.3 Feasibility of the standing-alone multi-use area

The costs of marine renewable are still very difficult to be accurately determined, given the present level of commercialisation of the wave energy devices. However, figures can be derived with some approximation from the COE tool developed by Chozas et al. (2014) for wave energy converters. The application of this tool to this case off-shore Venice leads to the total capex of 5,4 M€, the annual OpEx of 145,7 k€/y and the payback greater than 20 years. The previous study by Dalton et al. (2014), in cooperation with the Wavestar constructor team estimated the cost of the energy produced by one Wavestar C5 1000 kW WEC equal to 0.29 €/kWh from the application to a hypothetical case study. Even by assuming here that the cost of the energy produced by 3 platforms of Wavestar C5 600 kW are the same of the Wavestar C5 1000 kW, this energy cost is very far from the economically competitive cost of the energy produced by off-shore wind turbines that equals 0.05 €/kWh (Dalton et al. 2014). The payback period of the wave energy system is therefore very long, beyond the payback period of the fish farm, nevertheless it will still fall within the lifetime of the fish farm that can be estimated in a few tens of years.

7 Conclusions

Based on a hypothetical installation in one of the mildest area of the Mediterranean Sea, the Northern Adriatic, this paper examined the potential of offshore fish farms supported by marine renewable energy, in this case provided by an integration of small wind turbines (Libellula) and fixed wave

energy devices (WaveStar). The multi-use area is designed to fulfil the requirements of the fish farm and the constraints posed by the electrical infrastructure for power stabilisation and local storage. A critical issue for the design is the power discontinuity at the site, due to the mild climate, and the close correlation between wind and wave power, due to the wind-generated waves in the semi-enclosed Adriatic basin.

The electrical system required for the proper functioning and power stabilisation of the multi-use area consists of a GS, a H₂ storage system, a LPG storage tank, a BP and a DM. A new dedicated tool has been set-up to properly calculate the energy balance at each time step of the met-ocean data series and can be generally applied to any future study for a multi-use off-shore area.

In this specific case of bi-directional wave climate, the main axis of the multi-use area should be oriented almost perpendicularly to the two prevailing directions of incoming waves to maximise wave energy production and protection to aquaculture. Wave energy arrays are placed on the exposed side and around the fish farm cages, to exploit the limited protection offered to aquaculture in ordinary wave conditions.

The off-shore fish farm payback period is estimated of 10 years while the much greater payback of the wave energy devices would be however covered by the fish farm lifetime.

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